

Entrepreneurial Leadership and Employee Innovative Behavior: Maintaining Uncertainty in a Sport Organization

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The purpose of the study is to analyze the correlation between employee innovative behavior and entrepreneurial leadership behaviors in a sport organization situated in the Southernmost region of the United States of America. Data was collected from 80 full-time employees using the online survey methodology. The sampling technique utilized for the study was convenience sampling. Pearson's r correlation was utilized to test the correlation between employee innovative behavior and entrepreneurial leadership behaviors. The finding indicated that employee innovative behavior is positively correlated to entrepreneurial leadership behaviors in a sport organization, $r(80) = 0.856, p < 0.01$. The research study is concluded with a discussion of the results including practical implications and limitations of the study.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial leadership, employee innovative behavior, innovation, sport organization

According to theorists such as Akbari et al. (2021), studies concerning leadership styles and employee innovative behavior have become popular over recent years. Nonetheless, majority of these studies usually focus on types of leadership such as transformational leadership among others with relatively inconclusive results (Chen et al., 2016; Rego et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2019). Meanwhile, theorists such as Akbari et al. (2021) also commented that only a scant amount of empirical research has been done regarding entrepreneurial leadership and employee innovative behavior. Furthermore, more studies are needed across different types of organizations such as sports organizations to determine the mechanism by which employee innovative behavior is influenced by entrepreneurial leadership.

Zellweger and Zenger (2023) stated that studies relating to the subject of entrepreneurship over the years have influenced the notion of making decisions under uncertainty and risk. Thus, Hoskisson et al. (2017) opined that an entrepreneurial type of leadership tends to highlight how one usually navigates an uncertain climate, and the different behavioral approaches such as stimulating employee innovative behavior. Importantly, this usually makes the uncertainty particularly daunting for an entrepreneurial-type leader, unlike another type of leader, because the entrepreneurial leader usually pursues different goals, which might be conflicting and competing at the same time such as in the case of a particular sports organization (Hoskisson et al., 2017).

Bester (2012) stated that there are two main models of sport management to maintain the uncertainty in sports. Firstly, there is a

highly regulated model in which a particular sports organization might use a salary cap or a draft pick as in the case of the United States. Conversely, there is the lesser regulated model, in which a particular sport organization might use less regulation and a more laissez-faire type management. In essence, the particular sport tends to function independently. However, any issue of uncertainty is addressed occasionally by a particular governing body through intervention, as in the case of European countries (Chadwick, 2009). Both these models are reactive and not progressive in nature. Importantly, though, uncertainty is the foundation of a particular sport. The need for competition is critical for any sport to be successful. Hence, collaboration across the sports industry is recommended for its success in terms of the different organizational stakeholders involved and the particular sport itself (Bester, 20212).

For example, a key concept synonymous with collaboration across the sports industry is performance measurement (Bester, 2012). Because of constant public scrutiny, which tends to be accelerated by the mass media and general public outbursts, for instance, the use of technologically innovative behavior has made it easier to continuously measure particular facets of sports performance, enhancing this component in sport leadership (Bester, 2012). One might argue that this gives rise to employees exhibiting innovative behavior. Hence, the current research examines the correlation between employee innovative behavior and entrepreneurial leadership in a particular sport organization located in the Southern United States.

Review of Literature

Entrepreneurship Leadership Influence on Employee Innovative Behavior

It is telling that theorists such as Newman et al. (2018) opined that the new genre of leadership known as entrepreneurial leadership style is people-oriented. Importantly, entrepreneurial leadership is considered to be a critical factor to enhance and foster innovative behavior among employees (Fontana & Musa, 2017). Further, this employee's innovative behavior is responsible to implement and

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generate innovative solutions especially in nowadays unpredictable and competitive corporate environment (Gupta et al. 2004; Mia et al., 2018).

Over the years, the concept of innovation appears to be a main ingredient for organizations including sports organizations being competitive. As a result, theorists such as Amabile et al. (1996) opined that an organization is not successful only based on its traditional assets. It also tends to rely on its capability to consolidate expertise and knowledge. This is synonymous with “innovativeness” in an organization. However, there is a distinction between innovation and innovative behavior. For instance, theorists such as McLean (2005) commented that innovation in a particular organization tends to refer to the efficient application of novel solutions. Meanwhile, innovative behavior is the formulation of novel solutions, invaluable perspectives and ideology in different industries. More so, theorists such as Nazir et al. (2018) explained that innovative behavior appears to be risky and seems to thrive in an atmosphere of uncertainty. Further, this type of behavior is more accepted by a particular employee who is more committed to their organization. In essence, innovative behavior needs a positive rather than a negative working climate for collaboration and knowledge sharing (Muhammad & Sadia, 2016). This type of positive, though unpredictable, climate also breeds a higher level of organizational commitment and motivation in a particular employee (Bennett & Watson-Stewart, 2024).

Who is an Entrepreneurial Leader?

An entrepreneurial type leader is considered as one who enhances a particular employee's innovative behavior. In addition, one who tends to drive employee innovative performance in different types of organizations in varying industries (Fontana & Musa, 2017). In essence, one might argue that an entrepreneurial leader supports a particular employee to handle various obstacles and challenges. This is achieved when an employee engages in activities that are innovative in a particular type of organization (Freeman & Siegfried, 2015). However, it is noteworthy that there appears to be no common agreement in terms of the definition of this type of leadership. Meaning that theorists appear to be divided on the definition of this new type of leadership.

For example, some theorists such as Leitch and Volery (2017) opined that entrepreneurial leadership should be based on leadership skills or competencies. These skills, such as being proactive and intelligent in terms of risk taking are considered to be essential to enhance a particular organization's innovative capacity. Conversely, some theorists such as Middlebrooks (2015) opined that an entrepreneurial leadership should be based on distinctive leadership behaviors such as being transactional. Therefore, one might argue that leadership behaviors determine a particular leadership style necessary to accomplish entrepreneurial objectives including how an organization recognizes and exploits a particular entrepreneurial opportunity (Renko et al., 2015). Notwithstanding this, the present study examines entrepreneurial leadership style as an approach in which a particular leader directs and promotes entrepreneurial behaviors. In addition, that person acts as a role model, in that one displays entrepreneurial behaviors for others to follow. The following question and hypotheses will direct the present quantitative research.

- *RI*: Is there a positive correlation between employee innovative behavior and entrepreneurial leadership behaviors in a sport

organization situated in the Southernmost region of the United States of America?

- *H1*: Employee innovative behavior has a positive correlation with entrepreneurial leadership behaviors in a sport organization situated in the Southernmost region of the United States of America.
- *Ho*: Employee innovative behavior has no positive correlation with entrepreneurial leadership behaviors in a sport organization situated in the Southernmost region of the United States of America.

Method

Participants

The study recruited 80 full-time non-athlete participants (i.e., male & female participants in the age group of between 20 & 65 years) who voluntarily completed an online survey via the use of a link sent to their email addresses. Importantly, each participant knew beforehand that completing the survey was voluntary. Furthermore, the researcher maintained each participant's confidentiality in the study. The researcher was also familiar with the director of human resources management of the particular sports organization. Therefore, the sampling methodology used for the current study was the convenience sampling technique. For instance, Johnson and Christensen (2014) suggested that convenience sampling tends to be not too costly to implement, appropriate for data collection in a short period of time, and enable a researcher to have speedier access to the population at the particular organization being researched. Measure and Procedure

An online survey was utilized for data collection. This online survey comprised of three sections. One of the sections measured the qualitative demographic items including gender, year of employment, and educational level. Another section measured participants' self-report responses to entrepreneurial leadership. This scale consisted of eight items with a five-point Likert scale. This Likert scale had 1=“Never” to 5=“Always”. Importantly, this scale used to measure entrepreneurship leadership was conceptualized by Renko et al. (2015). It also had a reliability score of approximately 0.85. Third section measured participants' self-report responses to displaying innovative behavior. This scale consisted of six items with a five-point Likert scale. This Likert scale had 1=“Never” to 5=“Always”. Importantly, this scale used to measure participants' innovative behavior was conceptualized by Hu et al. (2009). It also had a reliability score of approximately 0.90.

The researcher was given access to potential participants' names and email addresses for a profitable and successful sport organization across different departments (HR, finance, sales, marketing, & IT) situated in the Southernmost region of the United States of America. These individuals also knew of the significance of the research. Although the research chose the convenience sampling methodology in terms of data collection. The researcher performed a power analysis to calculate the minimum size of the sample required. Sink and Myundudu (2010) posited that the power analysis is appropriate to determine the required sample size to perform the research with confidence in its findings. In addition, each participant needed to be working with the organization for at least one year with their present leader/manager. This is a requirement to make sure that each participant has spent ample time with the present leader/manager to assess their leadership style. The researcher

utilized the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 to calculate correlations as well as descriptive statistics.

Results

The researcher utilized the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 to compute correlations and descriptive statistics. Table 1 illustrates the research sample of 80 employees comprised of 50 males and 30 females. In terms of age group, 50 percent of the participants were between 35 and 39 years. Meanwhile, 20 percent were between 25 and 29 years, followed by 10 percent between 40-49 years. Next, 10 percent were 50 years or more, followed by 5 percent who were aged under 25 years and 5 percent were between 30 and 34 years. In assessing educational qualification, 60 percent had a bachelor's degree only, followed by 30 percent with a graduate degree. However, only 5 percent had a doctorate degree and the remaining percentage did not complete a college degree. The study had 50 percent of those who participated in the study worked at the organization between 10 and 15 years, followed by 30 percent of those who participated in the study worked at the organization between 5 and 10 years. Meanwhile, 15 percent of those who participated in the study worked at the organization between 1 and 5 years and the remaining 5 percent of those who participated in the study worked at the organization for at least 15 years.

The Pearson's *r* correlation analysis was conducted between the employee innovative behavior and entrepreneurial leadership scales to examine the research's H1 and H0: "Employee innovative behavior has a positive correlation with entrepreneurial leadership in a sport organization situated in the Southernmost region of the United States of America" and "Employee innovative behavior has no positive correlation with entrepreneurial leadership in a sport organization situated in the Southernmost region of the United States of America" respectively. Pearson's *r* correlation analysis indicated

that entrepreneurial leadership (independent variable) significantly correlated with employee innovative behavior (dependent variable), $r(80) = 0.868, p < .01$. Hence, the researcher accepted the alternate hypothesis, H1 (See Table 2). This finding was similar to previous studies done on the relationship between employee innovative behavior and entrepreneurial leadership (Arshi & Burns, 2018; Bagheri et al., 2020; Hughes et al., 2018).

Demographical Information

Table 1

Participants' Demographics in Sport Organizations

	Frequency Number	Percent
Gender		
Female	30	45%
Male	50	55%
Age		
< 25 years	4	5%
25 -29 years	16	20%
30 - 34 years	4	5%
35 - 39 years	40	50%
40 -49 years	8	10%
?50 years	8	10%
Education Level		
No College	4	5%
Bachelor's Degree Only	48	60%
Graduate Degree	24	30%
Doctorate Degree	4	5%
Working Years at the Organization		
Between 1and 5 years	12	15%
Between 5 and10 years	24	30%
Between 10 and 15 years	40	50%
≥15 years	4	5%

Table 2

Correlations Scores for Entrepreneurial Leadership and Employee Innovative Behavior

Pearson's r	Entrepreneurial leadership	Coefficient of Correlation	1.000	.868*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.068
		N	80	80
	Employee innovative behavior	Coefficient of Correlation	.868*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.068	.
		N	80	80

Note. *Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Discussion

The study explored the correlation between employee innovative behavior and entrepreneurial leadership behaviors in a sport organization situated in the Southernmost region of the United States of America. The research finding revealed that employee innovative behavior had a positive correlation with employee innovative behaviors in a particular sports organization. This finding was similar to previous studies done on the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and employee behavior, albeit with other types of organizations (Arshi & Burns, 2018; Bagheri et al., 2020; Hughes et al., 2018).

The study has significance in that this new approach to sport

management/leadership adds to the functional component as a determinant, which supports innovation in terms of employee innovative behavior in a particular sport organization. For example, theorists such as Mehmood et al. (2019) posited that an entrepreneurial leader creates a conducive organizational climate for innovation, which tends to empower and promote an employee to be innovative. This also untaps an innovative solution to a particular organizational challenge. One might argue that an organizational leader who applies the entrepreneurial leadership approach to one's task performance tends to encourage innovative behavior within one's subordinate. In essence, an entrepreneurial leader might guide innovative activity by fostering the formation and application of original and new ideas by a particular employee in an unpredictable

business environment. This applies to a sports organization because theorists such as Chadwick (2009) posited that a sports organization is different from a regular business organization in terms of the degree of uncertainty.

It is telling that sports organization strives on uncertainty of their outcome regarding the contest between a team or group of individuals. This uncertainty of who will be victors is what tends to draw fans, groups and sponsorship organizations to a particular sport activity or event (Chadwick, 2009). Therefore, an organizational leader of a sports organization is tasked to preserve this degree of uncertainty, which is the foundation of sport management and a sports organization (Chadwick, 2009). In essence, sport has transformed from a recreational activity to a profitable industry. However, organizational leaders (managers and senior managers) of sports organizations are responsible not only to keep cultural standards of sports. They are responsible for sustainability in terms of making profits. The main element of achieving this is through leadership that preserves uncertainty in outcomes in order to be profitable through innovation.

Nonetheless, this research study has some limitations. Firstly, the research only used a particular sports organization situated in the Southernmost region of the United States of America. This finding should not be generalized to every sports organization located in the Southern part of the United States. In addition, the study applied the definition of entrepreneurial leadership as an approach based on leadership behaviors rather than leadership skills.

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